

Studies on Thorium Tungstate Ion-exchanger

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In continuation of our work^{1,2} with insoluble tungstates, presently we have synthesised a granular variety of thorium tungstate (TT) suitable for column operation, prepared for the first time by Turnov and Kovba³. The preparation, properties and ion-exchange behaviour of crystalline variety of TT have also been studied by Qureshi and Nabi⁴ and De and Chowdhury⁵. The present work describes the exchange capacities and distribution coefficients of several cations on the granular variety of TT and useful separation of some binary mixtures of cations.

Results and Discussion

During the preparation of TT, pH of the reaction condition had negligible effect on the exchange capacity and also on the exchanger (Table 1).

TABLE 1—CONDITION OF SYNTHESIS AND A FEW PROPERTIES OF THORIUM TUNGSTATE

Sample no.	Concn. of reagents (M)		pH	Ion-exchange capacity for Na ⁺ /meq/g		Th : W ratio
	TN*	SW*		for Na ⁺ /meq/g		
				40°	80°	
1.	0.10	0.10	1	0.06	0.12	1 : 1.7
2.	0.10	0.10	2	0.10	0.20	1 : 1.8
3.	0.10	0.10	3	0.08	0.15	1 : 1.75
4.	0.10	0.10	4	0.05	0.10	1 : 1.7

*TN=thorium nitrate ; SW=sodium tungstate.

However, sample no. 2 has not only the highest ion-exchange capacity but also granular quality making it possible to use in column separations. Other products obtained were in very powdery form. Automatically, sample no. 2 was chosen for further studies. Thermal analysis of the sample shows that there is an initial loss of water near 100° corresponding to a broad endothermic peak, and also there is a small endothermic peak at 476° which may be due to the condensation of tungstate groups. A small exothermic peak at 633° is perhaps due to the formation of oxides. There is negligible loss of weight at about 450°. Ir spectra reveal similar features to those reported by earlier workers⁵. The pH-titration curve indicates a single break, corresponding to a monofunctional acid grouping.

The ion-exchange capacity of TT increased ($K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$) with decrease in hydrated radii of the exchanging alkali metal ions and alkaline earths cations (Table 2). Due to moderate heating, the exchange capacity increased with temperature (Table 1), probably due to loss in weight for the

TABLE 2—ION-EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF THORIUM TUNGSTATE

Metal ion	Hydrated radius Å	Ion-exchange capacity
Li ⁺	3.40	0.07
Na ⁺	2.76	0.10
K ⁺	2.32	0.12
Mg ²⁺	7.00	0.085
Ca ²⁺	6.80	0.09
Ba ²⁺	5.90	0.12

elimination of water. Radiation dose upto 50 M rad on the sample had no effect with respect to their exchange capacities. The compounds was found to be highly stable in different chemical environments, only a little amount of tungsten being released in the solution even with the treatment with 4 M mineral acids or 2 M alkalis. Moreover, it is found to be stable in solutions of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂, CaCl₂ and BaCl₂ and also in alcohol and benzene.

The values of K_D of several cations at different pH show that the adsorption of a cation is relatively more at higher pH. However, the trend is quite different from the earlier results and difficult separations could be achieved (Table 3). The principles of these separations are based on the high K_D values of Bi^{III}, Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} respectively in comparison to the other metal ions involved in these binary mixtures.

TABLE 3—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF METAL IONS ON THORIUM TUNGSTATE COLUMNS*

Sl. no.	Separation achieved	Metal ions taken (μg)	Eluent
1.	Bi ³⁺ -(Pb ²⁺ , Fe ²⁺ , Al ³⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Hg ²⁺)	Pb ²⁺ (2776.6) Fe ²⁺ (720.2) Al ³⁺ (446.2) Cu ²⁺ (1239) Zn ²⁺ (779) Cd ²⁺ (1236.4) Hg ²⁺ (2106.3) Bi ³⁺ (1864.3)	Pb ²⁺ , water ^a Fe ²⁺ , water ^a Al ³⁺ , water ^a Cu ²⁺ , water ^a Zn ²⁺ , water ^a Cd ²⁺ , water ^a Hg ²⁺ , water ^a Bi ³⁺ ; 2M HNO ₃
2.	Ti ⁴⁺ -(VO ²⁺ , Fe ²⁺ , Al ³⁺)	VO ²⁺ (546.4) Fe ²⁺ (720.2) Al ³⁺ (446.2) Ti ⁴⁺ (361.2)	VO ²⁺ ; water ^b Fe ²⁺ ; water ^b Al ³⁺ ; water ^a Ti ⁴⁺ ; 2M H ₂ SO ₄
3.	Zr ⁴⁺ -(UO ₂ ²⁺ , Ce ⁴⁺)	UO ₂ ²⁺ (201.4) Ce ⁴⁺ (196.8) Zr ⁴⁺ (225.2)	UO ₂ ²⁺ ; water ^a Ce ⁴⁺ ; water ^b Zr ⁴⁺ ; 2M HCl

*Exchanger used in column=5 g. ^apH=2. ^bpH=1.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A. R. grade. A Sambros 335 pH meter was used for pH measure-

ments. Spectral measurements were carried out using a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer, a Beckman (Acculab T.M.10) ir spectrophotometer and a Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrometer with MVU-1.

Preparation and studies with thorium tungstate: Granulated TT suitable for column operation was prepared as follows. To a solution (100 ml) of 0.1 M $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ in 2 M HNO_3 kept at 80° , 0.1 M sodium tungstate solution (200 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The resulting fine white precipitate was washed with demineralised water until pH of the washing was around 2 and dried at room temperature over silica gel. The samples of TT were fused with caustic soda and the fused mass was leached with water and filtered. The total filtrate was analysed for tungsten by the usual procedure⁶. The precipitate was dissolved in 4 N HCl and the solution was analysed for thorium⁷. A weighed amount (0.5 g) of TT (sample no. 2) was immersed in a mixed solution (50 ml) of varying ratio of (NaCl+NaOH) with intermittent shaking for 48 h at 25° , the strength of Na^+ being fixed at 0.1 N. The capacity of the exchanger was determined by equilibrating TT (0.5 g) with 2 M NaCl solution (5.0 ml) for 48 h. Similar values for several uni- and bivalent cations were also determined. Ir spectra was measured by the KBr disk method and thermal analysis was carried out at a heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$. The radiation stability of the exchanger was tested by determining the ion-exchange capacity of the material before and after subjecting it to a γ -radiation doses upto a maximum total dose of 50 M rad in a GC-900 γ -chamber, at BARC, India. The chemical stability was measured by equilibrating the exchanger (0.5 g) into different solvents (50 ml) for 48 h and determining the tungsten content of the solution by the spectrophotometric method⁸. In order to examine the affinity of TT (sample no. 2) toward various metal ions, distribution coefficients

for several cations were determined by equilibrating the exchanger (0.5 g) with solutions (50 ml each) of cations for 48 h at room temperature with intermittent shaking. Fe^{III} , Zr^{IV} , Ti^{IV} , Ce^{IV} and U^{VI} ions were determined spectrophotometrically⁸ and Hg by cold vapour AAS⁹. All other cations were determined by complexometric titration^{7,10,11}. For separation studies, glass columns (i.d., 1.5 cm) containing the ion-exchanger (5 g; 50–100 mesh) in the H^+ form were used.

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